

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New Quinazolinyl Thiazolidinones and Azetidinones

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Sequential treatment of anthranilic acid in pyridine with benzoyl chloride and hydrazine hydrate gives 2 that has been converted to azetidinones (4) and thiazolidinones (5) via the N-arylidene derivatives (3). Most of the compounds 4 and 5 showed moderate to good antimicrobial activity.

Quinazolines¹ and 4-thiazolidinones² possess biological activities. We wanted to study the effect of substitution of N³- position of quinazolinone nucleus with heterocyclic moieties, such as azetidinones and thiazolidinones on the biological activities.

The starting compound 3-aminoquinazol-4-one (2) was prepared by reacting 2-phenyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1) with hydrazine hydrate in pyridine. Treatment of 2 with various aldehydes in methanol in the presence of acetic acid gave the corresponding derivatives (3) which were converted to azetidinone (4) by cyclocondensation with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine in dioxane. The treatment of 3 with mercaptoacetic acid in presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂ in dimethylformamide gave the corresponding thiazolidinone derivatives (5).

Biological activity: All compounds (4 and 5) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus albus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebscilla pneumoniae* by cup-plate method³ at concentration of 1 mg ml⁻¹ in acetone. Compounds 4b, d, g, j (zone of inhibition = 10–16 mm) and 5a, b, c, d, g (10–18 mm) showed promising activity when compared with the standard streptomycin (14–19 mm) against all the bacteria.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (TFA/CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32

spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-Phenyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1): To a solution of anthranilic acid (0.1 mol) dissolved in pyridine (60 ml), benzoyl chloride (0.2 mol) was added. The mixture was stirred for 0.5 h followed by treatment with 5% NaHCO₃ (15 ml). The separated solid was crystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 120° (Found : C, 75.1; H, 4.0; N, 6.0. C₁₄H₉O₂N requires : C, 75.3; H, 4.1; N, 6.2 %); ν_{\max} 3 350 (NH), 1 780 (C=O), 1 680 (cyclic C=O) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 6.8–7.5 (9H, m, ArH).

3-Amino-2-phenylquinazol-4-one (2): A mixture of 2-phenyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (0.05 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.05 ml) in ethanol was refluxed for 3 h and cooled. The separated solid was crystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 196° (Found : C, 70.6; H, 4.5; N, 17.2. C₁₄H₁₁ON₃ requires : C, 70.8; H, 4.6; N, 17.4%); ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH₂), 1 680 (cyclic C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 4.5 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.7–7.4 (9H, m, ArH).

3-Arylidene-2-phenylquinazol-4-one (3d): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and 3,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h and the excess solvent then removed under reduced pressure. The residue was poured in ice-water and the separated solid crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 226° (Found : C, 63.2; H, 3.1; N, 10.5. C₂₁H₁₃ON₃Cl₂ requires : C, 63.4; H, 3.3; N, 10.6%); ν_{\max} 3 350 (NH), 1 680 (cyclic amido C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 5.8 (1H, s, -CH=), 6.8–7.5 (13H, m, ArH).

Scheme 1

1-(2'-Phenylquinazol-4'-on-3'-yl)-2-aryl-3-chloroazetid-4-one (4d): To a well-stirred solution of **3d** (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.002 mol), chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) was added at room temperature, the reaction mixture stirred for 0.5 h and refluxed for 3 h. The solution was then filtered to remove the insoluble solid salt. The filtrate was concentrated and titrated with ice-cold water, filtered and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 178° (Found: C, 58.4; H, 2.9; N, 8.7. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2N_3Cl_3$ requires: C, 58.7; H, 3.0; N, 8.9%); ν_{max} 1 780 (β -lactam C=O), 1 680 (cyclic C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 600 (C=C) and 760 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 3.8 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, CH), 5.27 (1H, d, J 4.5 Hz, CHCl) and 6.9–7.5 (14H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields

50–75%): **4a**, m.p. 190°; **b**, 199°; **c**, 189°; **e**, 210°; **f**, 182°; **g**, 161°; **h**, 187°; **i**, 201°; **j**, 216°.

3-(2'-Phenylquinazol-4'-on-3'-yl)-3-arylthiazolidin-4-one (5d): A mixture of **3d** (0.01 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) in THF (25 ml) containing a pinch of anhydrous $ZnCl_2$ was refluxed on a steam-bath for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured in ice-water, filtered and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 148° (Found: C, 58.6; H, 3.1; N, 8.6. $C_{23}H_{15}O_2N_3SCl_2$ requires: C, 58.9; H, 3.2; N, 8.8%); ν_{max} 1 710 (thiazolidinone C=O), 1 680 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 760 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 3.2 (1H, s, CH), 3.6 (2H, s, SCH_2) and 6.9–7.5 (14H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 45–70%): **5a**, m.p. 189°; **b**, 176°; **c**, 131°; **e**, 168°; **f**, 195°; **g**, 251°; **d**, **h**, 279°; **i**, 212°; **j**, 310°.

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